

Botanical Study on Importance of Mangrove Ecosystem for Conservation and Management Purposes

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Abstract

Mangrove forests are currently among the most threatened habitat in the world and are disappearing at an accelerated rate. More than one in six mangrove species worldwide are in danger of extinction due to coastal development and other factors, including climate change, logging and agriculture, according to the first-ever global assessment on the conservation status of mangroves for the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Rapid population growth and increasing utilization of mangrove habitats threaten in our country. Local societies along with their knowledge about the mangrove also are endangered while they are still underrepresented as scientific research. In the present study, local utilization pattern and perception of ecosystem change are documented. In this paper, general characteristic and special adaptation of mangrove, few medicinal and traditional uses of mangrove and support unique ecosystem of mangrove are reported.

Introduction

Mangroves are an easily recognized habitat along tropical and subtropical coastlines and brackish estuaries and deltas, where evergreen woody trees or shrubs thrive in the tide land mud or sand flats inundated daily with sea water. Scientists mention that the earliest mangrove species originated in the Indo-Malayan region. This is supported by the fact that there are more mangrove species present in this region than anywhere else in the world. About 110 species are characteristic plants of mangrove vegetation, out of more than 250,000 species of vascular plants. A wide variety of plant species can be found in mangrove habitat, but some 54 species in 20 genera, belonging to 16 families, constitute the "true mangroves", species that occur almost exclusively in mangrove habitats and rarely elsewhere (Hogarth, 1999).

Therefore, mangroves occur in more than 30 families of dicotyledons, as well as the monocotyledons, *Nypa* (a palm, family Arecaceae), *Crinum angustifolium* (family Amaryllidaceae), *Pandanus* (screw pines, family Pandanaceae) and ferns of the genus *Acrostichum*. Mangal along a tropical bay characteristically shows zonation. On the outfacing edge, fully exposed to high tides twice each day, called seaward zone, is inhabited by a small subset of tree species, *Sonneratia alba*, *Avicennia* spp., and *Rhizophora* spp. In the middle zone, members of the Rhizophoraceae, called *Rhizophora* zone or mesozone typically occur. The back, inland portion of mangal, also called the landward zone, which less frequently is covered by sea water and can receive freshwater from ground water or land runoff, is where the mangal associates can survive. There may be a gradual transition from mangal to terrestrial forest, but, in general, it does not appear that back mangal is merely a sere (stage) in succession from mangrove plants to a terrestrial forest.

Evolutionary convergence has resulted in many species of these plants finding similar solutions to the problems of variable salinity, tidal ranges (inundation), anaerobic soils (with no oxygen) and intense sunlight in the tropics.

Objectives

- To use natural resources systematically
- To conserve the mangrove ecosystem
- To give the knowledge of the adaptations mangroves have developed to better survive in their habitat

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- To give the information concerning traditional medicine which may be essential to produce the new drugs.

Methodology

The present study is based on intensive field excursion during 2009-2010. The plant specimens collected during this field trip were identified by available literature. The traditional medical practitioners were also consulted and ethnobotanical information presented here was gathered with the help of local informants and other elder of local people of this region. These data obtained were then analyzed carefully.

Study area

The study area is located in the coastal zone of Southern Rakhine State between $94^{\circ}27'21 - 94^{\circ}29'40$ E longitude and $17^{\circ}59'36 - 17^{\circ}59'57$ N-latitude.

Results

Biology of mangrove

Adaptations to Low Oxygen

Red mangroves, which can grow in the most inundated areas, prop themselves up above the water level with stilt roots, and can then take in air through slits in their bark (lenticils). Black mangroves live on higher ground, and make many pneumatophores (specialized root-like structures which stick up out of the soil like straws for breathing) which are covered in lenticils. There are four types of pneumatophore— stilt or prop type, snorkel or peg type, knee type and ribbon or plank type (Figure 1). Knee and ribbon types may be combined with buttress roots at the base of the tree. The roots also contain wide aerenchyma to facilitate oxygen transport within the plant.

Limiting Salt Intake

Red Mangroves exclude salt by having rather impermeable roots which are highly submersed, acting as an ultra-filtration mechanism to exclude Na salts from the rest of the plant. Water inside the plant shows that 90%, and in some cases of high salinity up to 97%, of the salt has been excluded at the roots. Any salt which does accumulate in the shoot is concentrated on old leaves which are then shed, as well as stored away safely in cell vacuoles.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1. Four types of pneumatophore of black mangrove (a) stilt or prop type, (b) snorkel or peg type, (c) knee type and (d) ribbon or plank type

Figure 2. Mangrove leaves exclude Na-salt on their leaves

Figure 3. Mangrove orientating their coriaceous leaves

Figure 4. Soil type for anaerobic bacteria

White (or Grey) Mangroves can secrete salts directly, they have two salt glands at each leaf base (hence their name - glands are covered in white salt crystals) (Figure 2).

Limiting Water Loss

Because of the limited availability of freshwater in the salty soils of the intertidal zone, mangrove plants have developed ways of limiting the amount of water that they lose through their leaves. They can restrict the opening of their stomata and also have the ability to vary the orientation of their leaves. By orientating their leaves to avoid the harsh midday sun, mangrove plants can reduce evaporation from their leaf surfaces (Figure 3).

Nutrient Uptake

The biggest problem that mangroves face is nutrient uptake. Due to the fact that the soil that mangroves live in is perpetually water logged, there is not much free oxygen available. At these low oxygen levels, anaerobic bacteria proceed to liberate nitrogen gas, soluble iron, inorganic phosphates, sulfides, and methane, which help contribute to a mangrove's particularly pungent odor and also make it a hostile environment to most plants. Since the soil (Figure 4) is not particularly nutritious, mangroves have adapted by modifying their roots. Prop root systems allow mangroves to take up gases directly from the atmosphere and various other nutrients. They quite often store gases directly inside the roots so that they can be processed even when the roots are submerged during high tide.

Increasing the Survival of their Offspring

All mangroves have buoyant seeds that are suited to dispersal in water. Unlike most plants, whose seeds germinate in the soil, many mangrove plants (e.g. Red Mangrove) are viviparous, that is, their seeds germinate while still attached to the parent tree (Figure 5). Once germinated, the seedling grows either within the fruit (eg. *Aegialitis*, *Acanthus*, *Avicennia* and *Aegiceras*), or without the fruit (eg. *Rhizophora*, *Ceriops*, *Bruguiera* and *Nypa*) which called propagule. When the propagule is mature it drops into the water where it can then be transported great distances. Propagules can survive desiccation and remain dormant for weeks, months, or even over a year until they arrive in a suitable environment. Once a propagule is ready to root, it will change its density so that the elongated shape now floats vertically rather than horizontally. In this position, it is more likely to become lodged in the mud and root.

Discussion and Conclusion

The tribal and rural people are entirely dependent on mangrove plants for their requirements. The inhabitants extensively exploit the mangrove plants for valuable timber and other requirements. On the other hand, the plant species are dwindling day by day due to merciless deforestation by traders for commercial interest. Over-exploitation of the forests is not only causing depletion of the plant resources but also disgracing the natural beauty of the region.

In addition, mangroves support unique ecosystems, especially on their intricate root systems. In areas where roots are permanently submerged, mangroves may be host to a wide variety of organisms, including algae, barnacles, oysters and sponges. Mangroves are excellent buffers between the violent ocean and the fragile coast, especially during hurricanes, which can bring powerful storm surges onto shores. The massive mangrove root system is quite efficient at dissipating wave energy. This root system also helps prevent coastal erosion.

Therefore, there is an urgent need for the conservation of mangrove plant wealth; it is suggested that the primary goals of conservation and protection of coastal mangrove forests are to increase public awareness and education about these habitats, provide designated conservation areas, and integrate coastal mangrove restoration into current coastal planning

(Figure 7). Mangrove plantations should be grown in coastal regions for the benefits they provide for coastal fisheries and other uses.

Figure 5. Attached fruit and germinated seedling

Figure 6. Seedling of mangrove

Bruguiera gymnorhiza (L.) Savigny

Heritiera fomes L.

Ceriops tagal (Perr.) C.B. Robinson

Figure 7. Actively exploited mangrove species

Table 1. Lists of Mangrove Species and their Uses in Folk Medicine

No.	Scientific Name/ Family	Ver. Name	Habit	Parts used	Uses
1.	<i>Acanthus ebracteatus</i> L. (Acanthaceae)	C&m (Kayar)	shrub	the whole plant	A decoction of the mucilaginous leaves and root is considered astringent, emollient and expectorant, against cough, asthma and rheumatism. The roots are used to treat chronic fever. The boiled seeds are commonly used, as an ingredient of a cough medicine. The roots and stems are used for skin diseases.
2.	<i>Acanthus illicifolius</i> L. (Acanthaceae)	C&m (Kayar)	shrub	the whole plant	The aerial parts are used a poultice on wound, and together with ginger, they are ground and put on sore legs, while porridge from them is taken for bowel complaints. A poultice of the leaves may be applied to treat rheumatic pain. The leaves, crushed in water, are drunk to facilitate delivery. A decoction of the leaves is used as a hair tonic.
3.	<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i> (L)Bl. (Myrsinaceae)	Asmyif (Bur-ban)	tree	wood	Construction materials, fire wood and charcoal
4.	<i>Aegialitis rotundifolia</i> Roxb. (Plumbaginaceae)	wmyif (Toke-ban)	tree	wood	Construction materials, fire wood and charcoal
5.	<i>Avicennia alba</i> L. (Avicenniaceae)	Orivri (Thame/ Lame)	tree	seed and wood	The wood is employed as making rice blocks for husking paddy, rice pounder and oil-mill. The black heart wood of old trees is powdered and used in ointment to treat headaches. The ashes of the burned wood are used as washing and cleaning for the treatment of small-pox.
6.	<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forsk.) Vierth. (Avicenniaceae)	Orivri (Thame/ Lame)	tree	seed and wood	The black heart wood of old trees is powdered and used in ointment to treat headache. The ashes of the burned wood are used as washing and cleaning for the treatment of small-pox. The unripe seeds are cooked with the leaves of <i>Ipomoea</i> , the seeds are bitter but edible after a preliminary preparation, generally by soaking in water for long period of time, and then often drying in the sunshine to eliminate the bitterness.

7.	<i>Avicennia officinalis</i> L (Avicenniaceae)	ဝဏ်းလှိုင် (Thame/ Lame)	tree	seed and wood	The black heart wood of old trees is powdered and used in ointment to treat headache. The ashes of the burned wood are used as washing and cleaning for the treatment of small-pox. The unripe seeds are cooked with the leaves of <i>Ipmoea</i> , the seeds are bitter but edible after a preliminary preparation, generally by soaking in water for long period of time, and then often drying in the sunshine to eliminate the bitterness. The bark is suitable for tanning leather and fishing nets. The wood are withstand attacks by termites and teredos. The bark is used for diarrhoea and malaria. The fruits are used as an astringent in betel quid when nothing better is available and they are used as an eye medicine. The peeled hypocotyles are eaten as vegetable after having been soaked in water and boiled.
8.	<i>Bruguiera gymnorhiza</i> (L.) Savigny (Rhizophoraceae)	အိတ်ဝပ်လှိုင် (Byu-u-talon)	tree	wood, bark, fruit and hypocotyles	The leaves are edible as salad for laxative and carminative. Bole is used as pole, fair wood and charcoal. Bark of this species was an important source of high quality tannin. A decoction of the bark is used to treat haemorrhages. The large scale exploitation of this species for posts, poles, firewood and charcoal has been widespread. Both bark and sap yield red dyes. The wood is used for tool handles and makes good firewood, but has been said to burn with too hot a flame for domestic use. It makes excellent charcoal. Making rope and fishing lines. The roots and bark are used as laxative and fish poison.
9.	<i>Cerbera odollam</i> Gaerth. (Apocynaceae)	ပုလဲ (Kalawar)	tree	leaves, wood	The roots grow in pitcher are added to betel quid to cure cough. A decoction of the whole plants is used to treat peptic, ulcers and liver dysfunction (treat enlarged liver). The leaves are crushed with salt to treat goitre. The latex and leaves in externally applications. e.g. ring worm, eczema, herpes and burns.
10.	<i>Ceriops decandra</i> (Griffith) Ding Hou. (Rhizophoraceae)	အိတ်သွင် (Baing daung phyu)	tree	wood, bark	
11.	<i>Ceriops tagal</i> (Perr.) C.B. Robinson (Rhizophoraceae)	မာမာ (Madama myaw)	tree	wood, bark	
12.	<i>Derris trifoliata</i> Lour. (Fabaceae)	မာမာ (Me gaung nwe)	lianas	stem fiber, root and bark	
13.	<i>Dischidia major</i> (Vahl.) Merr. (Asclepiadaceae)	ပုလဲ (U-sein nwe)	twining	the whole plant and latex	

14.	<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i> L. (Euphorbiaceae)	wa, map; yif (Ta yaw sae)	tree	latex bark, root, wood	Species contain highly irritating and poisonous substances, mostly latex. The latex is used as fish poison and as caustic for obstinate ulcer. The barks are used as an ingredient for dart poison and as a purgative. Chewing a little piece of bark will cause instant vomiting and purging but is generally considered to be too drastic a cure for constipation and the caution to reduce swellings on hands and feet. Very small amounts of the bark-juice are taken orally with coconut juice to treat pneumonia or asthma. The wood is used as a timber and charcoal.
15.	<i>Heritiera fomes</i> L. (Sterculiaceae)	uepi (Kanazo)	tree	wood and bark	Barks are applied as poultice on wound. The wood is extensively used for house contraction and for making household articles. A poultice of the leaves is applied externally to wounds, boils, ulcers, swellings, burns and rheumatism.
16.	<i>Hoya coronaria</i> Blume. (Asclepiadaceae)	za, mi; yif (Payoung ban)	climber	Leaves, latex	The latex is mixed with <i>Capsicum</i> leaves and taken internally to stimulate digestion and as a diuretic. A decoction of the leaves is used internally against cough, asthma and gonorrhoea.
17.	<i>Memecylon ovatum</i> Smith. (Melastomataceae)	a; t; yk; wif (Ye-o poke)	shrub	leaves, root	Chewed leaves are applied as poultice on wound. A decoction of leaves and roots are used for diarrhoea, dysentery and as an astringent. The leaves are used as a mordant before dyeing.
18.	<i>Nypa fruticans</i> (Thumb.) Wurmb. (Areaceae)	"ed (Dani)	tree palm	leaves, inflorescences and fruit	<i>Nypa</i> thatch from its leaves is rated superior to any other thatches. Jelly like sweetmeat from unripe endosperm is edible. <i>Nypa</i> ethanol (da ni ye) from the peduncle is drunk as beverage.
19.	<i>Phoenix paludosa</i> L. (Areaceae)	Oi; ay; jif (Thin baung)	tree palm	seed and shoot	Shoots are cooked as vegetable (salad). Seeds are also edible.
20.	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i> Bl. (Rhizophoraceae)	Al; aj; caw; m; j; zl (Byu chidauk phyu)	tree	wood, bark	The bark is an important source of tannin. It is used for tanning leather and to toughen and dye lines, nets and ropes used by fishermen. The wood is widely used local people for various types of household articles and fuel woods.

21.	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i> Lamk. (Rhizophoraceae)	အါ;အချာဝူဖ (Byu chidauk)	tree	wood, bark	The bark is an important source of tannin. It is used for tanning leather and to toughen and dye lines, nets, and ropes used by fishermen. It is also used as medicine in cases of haematuria. The wood is important for producing good quality charcoal, for firewood and construction materials. Leaves paste is used for rubbing on the joints to treat rheumatism or leaves occasionally eaten with curry. In literature - alkaloid and glycosides have been isolated from <i>S. globosa</i> ; these showed cytotoxic activity against human cervical carcinoma cell line.
22.	<i>Sarcolobus globosus</i> Wallich. (Asclepiadaceae)	ရဲဝဲလဲဝဲ (Malein tuk)	liana	leaves	Construction materials, fire wood and charcoal The bark of the bole is rich in tannin. It is used to dye cloth brown. The wood is used in boat building, and for nails, house-posts, small objects like tool handles, and for furniture. It can also be used as firewood. The astringent bark has some medicinal uses for dysentery, diarrhoea and other abdominal troubles.
23.	<i>Sonneratia alba</i> J. Sm. (Sonneratiaceae)	၁ရဲ (Lamu)	tree	wood	
24.	<i>Xylocarpus granatum</i> Koenig. (Meliaceae)	အဲတဲ ယိလ, တဲ (Ye ohn / Pinle ohn)	tree	leaves, barks	

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Dr. Hla Htay, Rector of Dagon University and Dr. Aye Aye Tun, Pro-Rector of Dagon University for their willing permission to present this research paper. I am also grateful to Dr. Than Than Htay, Professor and Head, Department of Botany, Dagon University, for her generous help in doing this work.

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